

EFFECT OF PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT ON FACULTY'S INNOVATIVE WORK BEHAVIOR: A MEDIATING ROLE OF ORGANIZATIONAL PRIDE

Khadijah Naveed^{*1}, Dr. Afia Saleem², Dr. Fatima Junaid³

^{*1}MBA Scholar (HRM), Institute of Management Sciences, Peshawar

²Assistant Professor, Institute of Management Sciences, Peshawar

³Senior Lecturer, Massey University, New Zealand

^{*1}khadijahn97@gmail.com, ²afia.salim@imsciences.edu.pk, ³fatimaajunaid@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15234433>

Keywords

Perceived Organizational Support, Innovative Work Behavior, Organizational Pride, Higher Education, Faculty Innovation.

Article History

Received on 08 March 2025

Accepted on 08 April 2025

Published on 17 April 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Khadijah Naveed^{*1}

Abstract

In the higher education sector, where faculty members are essential to promoting academic and institutional success, perceived organizational support (POS) is a substantial factor inducing employees' innovative work behavior (IWB). This study examines the connection between POS and IWB, focusing on the mediating role of organizational pride. Drawing from the Conservation of Resources (COR) theory and the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model, this study proposes that faculty members who experience strong organizational support grow to feel proud of their organization, which in turn encourages them to act in more creative ways. Faculty members of HEC-accredited business institutes in Peshawar, Pakistan, were surveyed using structured questionnaires as part of a cross-sectional quantitative approach. The findings indicate that POS and IWB have a significant positive correlation with organizational pride serving as a partial mediating factor. These findings highlight how crucial it is to create a positive work atmosphere and boost organizational pride in order to stimulate innovation in higher education. The necessity for institutions to put in place policies that enhance faculty support, acknowledge contributions, and foster a culture of pride and dedication are among the practical implications. Future studies should examine this relationship in a wider geographic setting and take into account more mediating factors.

INTRODUCTION

The extent to which workers feel their company appreciates their contributions and is concerned about their welfare is known as perceived organizational support (Rhoades and Eisenberger, 2002; Eisenberger et al., 1986). POS fosters a supportive environment that encourages risk-taking and creativity (Eisenberger et al., 1990). In the quick-paced business world of today, innovation has become a critical component for achieving long-term competitive advantage. Innovation makes a

significant impact in a person's performance and contributes to their success and survival (Ghardashi et al., 2019). Innovation is equally important in education sector. Teachers are the most important agents in enhancing the academic and social success of institutions, and by encouraging students' success, they contribute significantly to the success of educational institutions (Balker, 2015). Providing support and resources may help faculty within higher education to be more innovative at their workplace.

This relationship is an important one but has not been tested within higher education sector. According to Scott and Bruce (1994), innovative behaviors are those that entail the creation, marketing, and application of novel concepts or procedures inside a company. Those who feel connected and take pride in identifying with the organization are likely to be more innovative in their behaviours (Dutton et. al., 1994).

Contextualizing the Higher Education Setting:

Innovation in higher education is mission critical for improving teaching methods, research outputs, and administrative processes, therefore the role of faculty as primary drivers of innovation within universities is pivotal. In such a context it is timely to understand the interplay of POS, innovative behaviours and organisational pride, which is the aim and objective of this paper.

In order to gain a sustainable competitive advantage, Pakistan's Higher Education Commission (HEC) is concentrating on enhancing the teaching and research quality culture of Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs). Their primary goal is to foster innovative behavior in faculty members, which is centered on academic and practical research conducted in educational institutions as well as the development of teaching and learning strategies (Shahab & Imran, 2018). There have been several studies conducted on exploring the factors that influence the innovative work behavior of faculty at higher education institutions. Our study examined how POS, innovation behaviors, and organizational pride interact to affect the relationship between POS and IWB in Peshawar, KPK's higher education business institutions.

Theoretical underpinning:

Our research's underlying theory is founded on two viewpoints: job demands and resources theory and conservation of resources. According to the COR theory, people work hard to acquire, hold onto, and safeguard their resources. Resources can be things, traits, circumstances, or energies that the individual values (Hobfoll, 1989, Hobfoll et al., 1990). POS can be viewed as a valuable organizational resource. When faculty perceive strong organizational support, they feel valued and secure, leading to the

development of organizational pride. This pride, in turn, acts as a psychological resource that motivates faculty to engage in innovative behaviours to contribute positively to their organization. Additionally, according to JD-R theory, job characteristics can be divided into two separate groups: job resources (aspects of the job that aid in achieving work goals, lowering job demands, and promoting personal growth) and job demands (aspects of the job that require sustained effort). POS is a critical job resource that provides emotional and instrumental support, reducing the strain of job demands and promoting well-being. Organizational pride, fostered by POS, serves as a personal resource that enhances motivation and engagement, thereby encouraging innovative behaviors.

Literature Review:

Extant literature reports a significant positive association amongst POS and employees' innovative work behavior (e.g. Al-Taie & Khattak, 2024; Jamal, Begum, Alam & Hussain, 2023; Sulaiman, Ragheb & Wahba, 2019). Likewise, some other studies such as (Setton et al., 1996, Wayne et al., 1997) reveal that increased levels of POS inspire the employees to perform involuntary behaviors that are higher benefits to the organization such as innovation and creativity. Furthermore, according to some research, high POS levels make employees feel obligated to support their company by going above and beyond to deliver performance in the form of creative behaviors, job satisfaction, dedication, and citizenship behaviors (Eisenberger et al., 2002; Eisenberger and Rhoades, 2001; Rhoades et al., 2001).

Likewise, some studies report innovative work behavior as a continuous process rather than a one-time discrete activity through which employees along with working on their existing ideas also develop new ideas that is possible when they receive a continuous support from the organization (de Jong and Den Hartog, 2007; Afsar et al., 2016). Because POS makes employees feel like they are an essential part of the company, it is therefore argued that when employees feel strongly supported by the organization, they will engage in innovative work practices. Therefore, they feel a high sense of obligation to return in a similar way what they receive from the organization. Hence on the basis of

the above findings, the following hypothesis is postulated:

Direct Effect Hypothesis: POS has a positive direct effect on innovative behaviors among higher ED faculty.

Role of Organizational Pride:

Organizational pride, an area of study in psychology, is associated with how employees engage with their organization. Literature reports organizational pride as a significant resource that encourages constructive work practices and sets organizations apart in terms of competitiveness (Katzenbach, 2003). For example, it encompasses a positive work environment that includes social recognition, leading to increased employee dedication and a sense of pride (Kraemer & Gouthier, 2014; Carmeli, 2005). According to Goudarzi et al. (2011)'s study, organizational pride manifests in two forms. The first form is event-based, where employees experience brief, continuous emotional pride when the company achieves success. The second form is a general sense of pride in the company, leading to enduring and moral pride. Organisational pride is further divided into two categories by Kraemer and Gouthier (2014): emotional pride and attitudinal pride. A study by Durrah et al. (2020) examined the effects of organizational pride—both emotional and attitudinal—on the creativity of workers in Sultanate of Oman-based petrochemical companies. The findings showed that while emotional pride has no effect on creativity, attitudinal organizational pride directly and significantly influences it. Park and Shim (2019) studied the impact of CSR activities on flight attendants' emotions and attitudes in South Korean airline companies. Findings revealed that perceived CSR initiatives positively influence organizational pride and engagement. Furthermore, organizational pride mediates the relationship between perceived CSR efforts and organizational commitment. Emotional and attitudinal organizational pride were found to be significantly correlated by Goudarzi et al. (2011). Emotional pride directly influenced customer service commitment and inventiveness, while attitudinal pride directly impacted customer service commitment and turnover intention. Indirect effects on creativity were also observed.

Summing up, perceived organizational support (POS) has a significant impact over individual's innovative work behavior (Eisenberger et al., 1986, Rhoades and Eisenberger, 2002). POS of employees can be enhanced if they receive enough support from their organization, supervisor and peer. While we know through Job-Demands Resource Model, that POS leads to better employee behaviours (Bon & Shire, 2022), we argue that it can lead to more innovative behaviours. We further build on Conservation of Resources Theory that there are strong link of POS with positive employee outcomes when they are supported as they are able to conserve resources. As POS rises, so do organizational commitment, job satisfaction, organizational citizenship, job involvement, work engagement, and individual innovation (Doğru, 2018).

Mediating Role of Organizational Pride:

Mediating variables are critical in development and application of positive organizational behaviours to foster better organizational performance. According to Kaplan and Nortan (1996) organizations should incorporate non financial measures such as organizational support, flexible working hours to facilitate and increase the employee's productivity. Hence, we infer that the organizational support influences the feelings of employees who feel proud of their organization for providing them a positive working environment that results in to positive workplace behaviours such as innovation and creativity.

Numerous studies back up our claim, for instance. Work-life balance, organizational pride, job satisfaction, and startup team performance were all examined by Park and Shim (2019). The results of their study showed that supervisory support and team trust positively impacted work-life balance, while the effect of autonomy was inconclusive. Thus, a positive working environment such as work-life balance enhanced the employees' feelings in form of organizational pride resulting in to greater job satisfaction, and team performance. Similarly, in the context of advertising agencies, Arshad et al. (2016) looked into the connection between employee creativity, organizational pride, and organizational morality. The study revealed that organizational

morality positively influenced employee creativity, partially mediated by organizational pride.

To conclude, from the Conservation of resources and job demands and resources perspective, POS is a valuable resource of the organization. A strong supportive culture initiate change in employees' feelings of pride that motivates them to generate innovative techniques and ideas for increased organizational performance. Therefore, based on the literature mentioned above, we deduce the following hypothesis:

Indirect effect: Organizational pride mediates the relationship between POS and innovative behaviours.

Methodology and data Collection:

The research methodology employed is quantitative since the current study was performed to test an existing theory in the form of research hypotheses rather than to develop a new theory. Deductive reasoning is used to test theories, which entails reading a theory in depth and then limiting it down to a hypothesis. Because the data used to test the hypothesis was obtained at a single moment in time, it is a cross sectional research. Data collection was done through structured questionnaires.

The study focused on faculty members of HEC-recognized business institutes in Peshawar, including both public and private universities. The population consisted of faculty from 11 institutes, 5 public and 6 private sector universities. The research scope was limited to the Peshawar region, with public universities such as IMS, Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Women University, Islamia College University, and IBMS, and private institutes including SUIT, CUSIT, Brains Institute Peshawar, Abasyn University, Cecos

University, and Iqra National University. During the data collection phase, a census was conducted to gather information. A census is a method that allows for comprehensive data collection on all or most aspects of the population. It focuses on gathering precise information about each unit by encompassing the entire population. This approach ensures that every aspect of the population is considered, resulting in more accurate and reliable conclusions.

Measures:

The Rhoades, Eisenberger, and Armeli (2001) inventory was used to gauge respondents' answers on the POS. It consists of eight questions designed to predict the respondent's opinion about the support received by his or her organization. Likewise, Innovative work behaviour the inventory by Scott and Bruce's (1994) was used to measure responses regarding innovative work behaviors of the teachers. Based on Kanter's (1988) work on the stages of innovation, it consists of nine questions, three of which deal with idea generation, three with concept promotion, and three with idea realization. Similarly, respondent's responses on Organizational pride the inventory by Gouthier and Rhein (2011) was used which consists of 7 items. A 5-point Likert scale, with 1 denoting strongly disagree, 2 disagree, 3 neutral, 4 agree, and 5 strongly agree, was used to collect all of the responses. The instruments were thoroughly tested, as were the subscales. According to Sekaran (2003), reliability of a measure is achieved when all respondents give the same overall meaning to the item. The table below summarizes the reliability statistics for POS, Organizational Pride and IWB.

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

S.no	Research instruments	No.of items	Cronbach alpha α
1.	POS	8	.676
2.	IWB	9	.942
3.	Organizational pride	7	.904

* $\alpha \geq 0.6$ hence, instruments are reliable.

A value of Cronbach's alpha greater than 0.6 is considered a high reliability and acceptable index (Nunnally, 1994). The test reliability of all three instruments is largely acceptable and dependable, as indicated in Table 1 above (Nunnally, 1994).

Statistical analysis:

This research investigates the impact of perceived organisational support on faculty's innovative work behaviour. It also looks at how organizational pride functions as a mediator in the relationship between faculty members' innovative work practices and their perceptions of organizational support. Hence in

order to test the direct effect hypothesis i.e. the effect of POS on employees' innovative work behavior linear regression analysis was performed. However, the indirect hypothesis i.e. the mediating effect of pride on POS to innovative work behavior was examined with Baron and Kenny's method. Additionally, the Sobel test was used to further confirm the mediation effect's significance. The

following section explains the statistical analysis performed for testing the direct and indirect effect hypotheses of the current study.

Descriptive Analysis:

Data was tested in SPSS using Regression, descriptive statistics, and frequencies.

Table 2: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

	Frequency (%)	
Gender	Male	64.9
	Female	35.1
Age	25-35	74.7
	36-45	20.1
	46-55	5.2
	55 and over	0.00
Qualification	Bachelors	2.6
	Master	12.3
	MS	68.8
	PHD	16.2

Table 2 show that males outnumber females. The frequency percentage confirms the results, indicating that 64.9 percent of the respondents are males and 35.1 percent are females. Majority of the respondents fall in the age category of 25 to 35. Also, majority of the respondents have done MS i.e., 68.8 percent.

initial significant relationship between the independent and dependent variables gets reduced when the mediator is taken into account. This is known as partial mediation. This suggests that even though the mediator accounts for a portion of the relationship, the independent variable still has a direct impact on the dependent variable. In these cases, the independent variable's impact on the dependent variable is partially explained by the mediator, indicating that both direct and indirect pathways play a role in the relationship as a whole. This study examines how faculty members' innovative work practices are impacted by their perceptions of organizational support. It also looks at how organizational pride functions as a mediator in the relationship between faculty members' creative work practices and their perceptions of organizational support. Because no prior study has examined the impact of these variables, it is set in the context of Peshawar, Pakistan.

Hypotheses testing:

Regression analysis is used to figure out how dependent and independent variables are related, as well as the changes that take place in the dependent variable as a result of changes in the independent variable.

Mediation effect is investigated using the Barron and Kenny (1986) approach. It involves a four-step regression analysis to examine the association between the predictor and criterion variables. Complete mediation occurs when the mediator makes the initial association insignificant and the association with the moderator significant. The

Table 3: Association between POS and IWB

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	(P≤0.05)	(β)	T	(P≤0.05)
H1: (Y.x)	0.427	0.183	0.177	33.942	0.000	0.427	5.826	0.000

Table 4: Mediation Analysis

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	(P≤0.05)	(β)	T	(P≤0.05)
H2: (Ym.X)	0.782	0.612	0.607	118.958	0.000	0.151	2.736	0.007
H2a: (Xm)	0.389	0.151	0.146	27.103	0.000	0.389	5.206	0.000
H2b: (mY)	0.770	0.592	0.590	220.998	0.000	0.770	14.866	0.000

Table 5: Sobel Test

Sobel	Value	(P≤0.05)
	4.83	0.000

The significance of the relationship between the independent variable (POS) and the dependent variable (IWB) was tested using Baron and Kenny's methodology. The R square value in Table 3 indicates that POS explains 18.3% of the variation in IWB. The model is highly significant (F=33.942, p=0.000) and can be used to predict the outcome variable. The beta value (Beta=0.427) confirms that POS has a significant effect on faculty's IWB. For every unit increase in perceived organizational support, the faculties innovative work behavior increases by 0.427 points. These findings support the first hypothesis.

The next steps of Baron and Kenny's (1986) approach were conducted to analyze the mediation. Table 4 shows a significant relationship between the predictor variable and mediator (F=27.103, p=0.000). The mediator is highly associated with the dependent variable (F=220.998, p<0.05) and explains 59% of the variation in dependent variable. Therefore, this result confirms our first hypothesis that POS has a positive effect on employees' innovative work behaviors.

In the final step, a multiple regression was conducted to test the second hypothesis of our study that examined the mediated effect of pride on POS and innovative work behaviors. The results of our data analysis depicted that the addition of the mediator reduced the beta value of the predictor variable from 0.427 to 0.151. Although the relationship between the dependent and independent variables remained significant (F=118.958, p=0.007, see table-4), hence, it was concluded that the employees' pride partially

mediated the relationship between POS and innovative work behaviours.

The mediation effect was further assessed using the Sobel test, which indicated a significant indirect effect (p-value=0.000) after introducing the mediator (organizational pride). The results of the Sobel test (T-statistics=4.83, p-value=0.000) further confirmed the presence of mediation. Previous studies (MacKinnon and Dwyer, 1993; Stone and Sobel, 1990) have discussed the statistical power and reliability of the Sobel test. Hence, the analysis of our data provided sufficient evidences to confirm organizational pride as a mediator between POS and IWB therefore the second hypothesis of our study was also accepted.

Discussion:

The study's findings indicate that POS influences faculty members' IWB through the mediating factor of organizational pride. When instructors perceive positive support and value from their organization, they exhibit positive work behavior and creativity. This is consistent with previous research that suggests employees' perception of their company influences their commitment and sense of organizational pride (Carmeli, 2005). Therefore, the hypothesis stating that POS has a positive effect on faculty IWB through organizational pride is supported by the study's results.

According to Agarwal (2004), one of the factors associated to employees' IWB is their POS. Al-Omar et al. (2019) discovered a strong connection between employee engagement and POS. Suseno, Standing, Gengatharen, and Nguyen (2020) found that

organizational support, among other factors, positively influenced innovative work behavior. Additionally, teachers' perceptions of organizational support are considered an indicator of their commitment to the organization (Nayir, 2012).

In order to maintain a competitive edge, Pakistan's Higher Education Commission (HEC) is working on improving the teaching and research quality culture of Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs). Their main focus is on fostering faculty innovation, which is based on academic and practical research in educational institutions as well as developing teaching and learning methodologies (Shahab & Imran, 2018).

Organizational Pride has favorable workplace effects as well and its mediating function has been studied in many studies. The organizational pride can help motivate Lecturer Performance to improve. The greater the Organization's pride, the better the Lecturers' performance (Nadati et al., 2019). Arshad et al., (2016) discovered that the association between corporate morality and employee creativity is partially mediated by organizational pride. The sole aspect of organizational pride that directly and significantly boosts creativity is attitudinal (Durrah et al., 2020).

Thus, based on the positive consequences of POS and organizational pride, the current study confirms that POS leads to positive workplace behavior, one of which is innovative work behavior. It has also been confirmed that organizational pride plays a mediating function in the POS-IWB link.

Implications for Practice:

Suggest practical steps higher education institutions can take to enhance POS and organizational pride to foster innovative behaviors among faculty. This could entail offering chances for professional growth, acknowledging and rewarding contributions, and fostering a positive work atmosphere.

The findings of our study indicate practitioners that they should provide maximum support to their employees in terms of being careful for their well-being and emotional needs because it influences the employees' feelings of pride that as a result increases their ability to perform better in form of innovative work behaviours. Hence at individual level, training programs are essential to increase the faculty

awareness regarding the importance of providing adequate support both emotional and instrumental, whenever it is needed by their colleagues at workplace. Moreover, at organizational level, the establishment of a supportive culture should remain one of the primary objectives of the organization that should not only recognize but also attend employee needs.

Lastly, the higher education institutions should not neglect the importance of a fair reward system while promoting positive employee behaviours such as innovation and creativity at work place. By incorporating acknowledgment and incentives for innovative work behaviours can serve to reinforce the faculty to such an optimal performance.

Future Research directions:

In order to determine whether or not POS significantly influences faculty members' innovative work practices, it is advised that future researchers carry out the same study across the country with a larger sample size. Also, whether organizational pride has any mediating effect between POS and IWB. An additional suggestion is to carry out a comparative analysis by concentrating on the respondents' gender in order to find out how each gender reacts to POS and how it affects their IWB through organizational pride. As our study was a cross-sectional study therefore, the same variables and hypothesis should be the subject of longitudinal research, in which data is collected repeatedly over time to observe the relationship between the variables. Moreover, our research investigated the direct effect of POS and mediating effect of Organizational pride over innovative work behaviour. However, it is recommended that additional factors that can affect and guarantee the innovative work practices of higher education faculty be found in order to obtain more profound understanding.

Conclusion:

Our study contributes to extant literature on perceived organizational support by incorporating the notion of feelings of pride at work as a crucial mechanism that ensures innovative work behaviours in the presence of organizational support. Moreover, the COR and JDR theories are enhanced by the inclusion of organizational pride as a significant

intangible psychological resource that generates positive outcomes in form of innovative work behaviours when the adequate supply of job resources in form of organizational support is ensured.

REFERENCES

- Afsar, B., Badir, Y., & Kiani, U. S. (2016). Linking spiritual leadership and employee pro-environmental behavior: the influence of workplace spirituality, intrinsic motivation, and environmental passion. *J. Environ. Psychol.* 45, 79-88.
- Agarwal, U. A. (2014). Examining the impact of social exchange relationships on innovative work behaviour: Role of work engagement. *Team Performance Management.*
- Al-Omar, H.A., Arafah, A.M., Barkat, J.M., Almutairi, R.D., Khurshid, F & Alsultan, M.s. (2019). The impact of perceived organizational support and resilience on pharmacists' engagement in their stressful and competitive workplaces in Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal*, 27, 1044-1052.
- Al-Taie, M., & Khattak, M.N. (2024) The impact of perceived organizational support and human resources practices on innovative work behavior: does gender matter? *Front. Psychol.* 15:1401916.
- Arshad, A., & Imran, A. (2016). Impact of organizational morality on employee creativity: mediating role of organizational pride. *International Review of Management and Business Research*, 5 (3), 961-971.
- Balker, B. (2015). The relationships between organizational climate, innovative behavior and job performance. *International Online Journal of Educational Sciences*, 7(2), 81-92.
- Barron, R. M., & Kenny, D. A. (1986). The moderator-mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51, 1173-1182.
- Bon, A.T. & Shire, A.M. (2022). Review of Conservation of Resources Theory in Job Demands and Resources Model. *International Journal of Global Optimization and Its Application*, 1(4), 236-248
- Carmeli, A. (2005). Perceived external prestige, affective commitment, and citizenship behaviors. *Organization studies*, 26(3), 443-464.
- De Jong, J., & Den Hartog, D. (2010). Measuring Innovative Work Behaviour. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, 19, 23-36.
- Doğru, Ç. (2018). The relationship between perceived support and innovative behavior: Analyzing the mediating role of work engagement. *İşletme Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 10(2), 384-402.
- Durrah, O., Allil, K., Gharib, M., & Hannawi, S. (2020). Organizational pride as an antecedent of employee creativity in the petrochemical industry. *European Journal of Innovation Management.*
- Dutton, J. E., Dukerich, J. M., & Harquail, C. V. (1994). Organizational images and member identification. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 39(2), 239-263.
- Eisenberger, R., Fasolo, P., & Davis-LaMastro, V. (1990). Perceived organizational support and employee diligence, commitment, and innovation. *J. Appl. Psychol.* 75, 51-59. doi: 10.1037/0021-9010.75.1.51
- Eisenberger, R., Huntington, R., Hutchison, S., & Sowa, D. (1986). Perceived organizational support. *Journal of Applied psychology*, 71(3), 500.
- Eisenberger, R., & Rhoades, L. (2001). Incremental effects of reward on creativity. *J. Pers. Soc. Psychol.* 81, 728-741.
- Eisenberger, R., Stinglhamber, F., Vandenberghe, C., Sucharski, I. L., & Rhoades, L. (2002). Perceived supervisor support: contributions to perceived organizational support and employee retention. *J. Appl. Psychol.* 87, 565-573
- Ghardashi, F., Yaghoubi, M., Bahadori, M., & Teymourzadeh, E. (2019). Innovation capability in medical sciences universities: A qualitative study of Iran. *Journal of education and health promotion*, 8.

- Goudarzi, K., Llosa, S., Orsingher, C., Gouthier, M. H., & Rhein, M. (2011). Organizational pride and its positive effects on employee behavior. *Journal of Service Management*.
- Gouthier, M.H., & Rhein, M. (2011). Organizational pride and its positive effects on employee behavior. *Journal of Service Management*, 22,(5),633-649.
- Hobfoll, S. E. (1989). Conservation of resources: A new attempt at conceptualizing stress. *American Psychologist*, 44, 513-524. doi:10.1037/0003-066x.44.3.513
- Hobfoll, S. E., Freedy, J., Lane, C., & Geller, P. (1990). Conservation of social resources: Social support resource theory. *Journal of Social and Personal Relationships*, 7, 465-478.
- Jamal,A., Begum,S., Alam.,H & Hussain,T. (2023). Impact of perceived organizational support on innovative work behavior and burnout in teachers: Thriving at work as the mediator. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 10(2), 288-307.
- Kanter, R. M. (1988). When a thousand flowers bloom: Structural, collective, and social conditions for innovation in organizations. *Knowledge Management and Organizational Design*, 10, 93-131.
- Kaplan, Robert S., & Norton, David P. (1996). Using the balanced scorecard as a strategic management system: Harvard business review Boston.
- Katzenbach, J. (2003). Pride: a strategic asset. *Strategy & Leadership*.
- Kraemer, T., & Gouthier, M. H. (2014). How organizational pride and emotional exhaustion explain turnover intentions in call centers. *Journal of Service Management*.
- MacKinnon, D. P., & Dwyer, J. H. (1993). Estimating mediated effects in prevention studies. *Evaluation review*, 17(2), 144-158.
- Nadatien, I., Handoyo, S., Pudjirahardjo, W. J., & Rahayu, Y. P. (2019). The influence of organizational pride on the performance of lecturers in health at the Nahdlatul Ulama university in Surabaya. *Indian Journal of Public Health Research & Development*, 10(1), 538-542.
- Nayir,F.(2012). The relationship between perceived organizational support and teachers' organizational commitment. *Egitim Arastirmalari-Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 48, 97-116.
- Nunnally, J. C. (1994). *Psychometric theory* 3E. Tata McGraw-hill education.
- Park, J. G., & Shim, J. S. (2019). An Effect of Work and Life Balance of Startup: Focus on Organizational Pride and Job Satisfaction. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business*, 10(3), 95-112.
- Rhoades, L. & Eisenberger, R. (2002) Perceived Organizational Support: A Review of the Literature. *The Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87, 698-714.
- Rhoades, L., Eisenberger, R., & Armeli, S. (2001). Affective commitment to the organization: The contribution of perceived organizational support. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86, 825-836.
- Scott, S. G., & Bruce, R. A. (1994). Determinants of innovative behavior: A path model of individual innovation in the workplace. *Academy of management journal*, 37(3), 580-607.
- Sekaran, U. (2003). *Research Methods for Business: A Skill-Building Approach*. John Wiley & Sons, Incorporated, USA
- Settoon, R. P., Bennett, N., & Liden, R. C. (1996). Social exchange in organizations: perceived organizational support, leader-member exchange, and employee reciprocity. *J. Appl. Psychol.* 81, 219-227.
- Shahab, H., & Imran, R. (2018). Cultivating University Teachers' Innovative Work Behavior: The Case of Pakistan. *Business and Economic Review*, 10(1), 159-177.
- Stone, C. A., & Sobel, M. E. (1990). The robustness of estimates of total indirect effects in covariance structure models estimated by maximum. *Psychometrika*, 55(2), 337-352.
- Sulaiman, M., Ragheb,M.A & Wahba,M. Perceived Organization Support Role in Creating an Innovative Work Behavior. *Open Access Library Journal*, 6: e5372.
- Suseno, Y., Standing, C., Gengatharen, D., & Nguyen, D. (2020). Innovative work

behaviour in the public sector: the roles of task characteristics, social support, and proactivity. *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 79(1), 41-59.

Wayne, S. J., Shore, L. M., & Liden, R. C. (1997). Perceived organizational support and leader-member exchange: a social exchange perspective. *Acad. Manag. J.* 40, 82-111.

